

A Bird's-Eye View of the Sociolinguistic Landscape of Seychelles

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1. Introduction

Seychelles is an archipelago of 115 islands located in the Indian Ocean, northeast of Madagascar and off the eastern coast of Africa. With a population of approximately 100,000 people, it is one of the smallest countries in both size¹ and population in the African region. The majority of Seychellois reside on the largest island, Mahé, where the capital city, Victoria, is situated. The economy is primarily driven by tourism and fisheries, supplemented by agriculture and offshore financial services. The natural beauty of the islands, characterized by tropical beaches, coral reefs, and lush forests, forms the backbone of the country's appeal to visitors and contributes significantly to its economic activities.

Seychelles is a culturally diverse nation, shaped by its history of African, European, and Asian influences. This blend is reflected in the customs, cuisine, music, and religious practices of the people. Roman Catholicism is the predominant religion, followed by Anglicanism, Hinduism, Bahai, and Islam, reflecting a pluralistic religious landscape. The cultural and linguistic profile of the country is equally rich and distinctive. The sociolinguistic environment of Seychelles is defined by its official trilingualism: Seychellois Creole (hereafter referred to as Kreol Seselwa), English, and French. While Kreol Seselwa is the most widely spoken language in everyday life, and serves as a marker of national identity, English, and to a lesser extent French, are prominent in formal domains such as education, government, and media. It is also to be noted that there are several minority languages present in the language ecology, the most prominent of which are Gujarati (1.9%), Hindi (1.8%) and Tamil (0.9%) spoken in the Indian community (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). The interplay of languages looks very different depending on what domain we look at, something which highlights the dynamic and complex multilingual fabric of Seychelles.

The aim of this article is to give an overview of the sociolinguistic landscape of Seychelles. To do so, a brief historical account of various aspects relevant to the current language ecology is provided. This section is followed by specific descriptions of the language practices in different domains including politics, the judiciary, education, media, religion as well as the language practices 'in the street' and of everyday informal communication. The article ends with a summarized overview of the language ecology and with a

¹ Note that while the land mass of the Seychelles is very small (455 km²), the sea area covers almost 400,000 km².

discussion of the ideologies governing language choices. The article closes with speculations about possible future language developments and points to areas of unexplored sociolinguistic research.

2. Historical background

The early history of Seychelles is marked by a lack of indigenous inhabitants; the islands were uninhabited until the 18th century. Although Arab sailors and Portuguese explorers had passed through the region, permanent settlement only began with the French in 1770, when a small group of settlers with captive slaves moved from Mauritius to establish a colony with the aim to grow spices (Scarr, 2000). Over the following years the population grew rapidly, partly a result of the islands being used as a depot for smuggled slaves, and when the islands formally became a British colony in 1814 under the Treaty of Paris, the population had reached 7,000. The population was largely (85-90%) made up of slaves governed by a relatively small group of primarily French-speaking landowners (Scarr, 2000; Fleischmann, 2008). This situation continued until 1835, when slavery was finally abolished by the British. At this time, according to Medeiros (2003, pp.65-68), there were 6,521 slaves in the Seychelles: 3,924 from Mozambique, 2,231 Creoles (born in the Seychelles or Mauritius), 282 from Madagascar and 28 from India. In the years that followed, the Royal Navy intercepted slave ships, releasing freed slaves in Seychelles. Just between the years 1861-1875 more than 2,500 freed slaves settled on the islands (Harms et al., 2013).

This early mix of population laid the foundation for the linguistic landscape of Seychelles. French was initially the language of administration and the elite, while African slaves brought diverse linguistic influences from their native tongues. It should be noted here that the slaves were generally forbidden to speak African languages in the colonies by the French colonizers (Fleischmann, 2008, pp 34 -35). This imposition and demonstration of the colonizers' supremacy is significant as it influenced the view of Kreol Seselwa as an inferior language, often called 'patois'. Over time, these linguistic elements blended with French to form Kreol Seselwa that developed as the primary means of communication among the diverse population. This creolization process shaped the linguistic identity of Seychelles, making Kreol Seselwa not just a language of daily interaction but also a symbol of cultural unity and resistance against colonial hierarchies (Bollée,1993; Chaudenson, 2001). Noteworthy here is also the fact that many of the early population (slaves as well as landowners) were migrants from Mauritius and Réunion, where creolization of French had already begun.

As a marginal colony of little importance, Seychelles was largely left its own devices; the British presence was mainly restricted to the administrative sphere, where English also became the official language. French, however, kept its role in many domains including religious practice and high culture, areas controlled by the francophone elite of colonial

descent, the ‘white bourgeoisie’, or the so-called *Grands Blancs* (Bollée, 1993, p.88). French was also the medium of instruction in education until the 1940s, when the church-owned schools were finally replaced by more formal and organized arrangements, based on the English system and language (Fleischmann, 2008, p.74). During the entire colonial period, Kreol Seselwa, though used in everyday communication amongst most of the population, remained a low status language, and only existed in its spoken form.

According to Deutschmann and Zelime (2022), the language situation in pre-independence Seychelles was a direct reflection of the power structures: the British ruled administratively, while the French *Grand Blancs* descendants retained economic and cultural influence. Access to power in administration, law, religion, and education required proficiency in English and, to a lesser extent, French. Despite this, Kreol Seselwa remained the mother tongue of the majority, serving as a marker of Creole identity, distinct from the ruling colonial cultures.

With independence in 1976 and the subsequent 1977 coup d’etat and one-party system of governance, Kreol Seselwa gained official status in administration, culture, and education, playing a key role in the nation-building process (Moumou, 2004). Efforts to elevate its status included Seychelles' involvement in the *Federasyon Bann zil Kreol* in 1981, and the establishment of International Creole Day in 1982, which expanded into the Creole Festival in 1985. Kreol Seselwa underwent rapid standardization, saw translations of key literary works, and was recognized as an official language with a role in education. In this domain, Kreol Seselwa was introduced as medium of instruction from Primary 1-4 and was also taught as a separate subject until Primary 6. As is discussed in 3.4 below, recent years, however, have seen a marked decline of the role of Kreol Seselwa in education.

3. Overview of the current language ecology

Below, follows a description of the current language practices in different ‘domains’ to give a brief contextual understanding of the sociolinguistics of Seychelles. According to Spolsky (2009), domains can be visualized as variants of discourse shaped by aspects such as professional context, history, location, content and subject, resulting in pockets of specific language practices. Examples include the language practices in contexts such as politics, religion and education. It is impossible to give an exact representation of all the languaging that is going on in a complex community. All descriptions in sections 3.1-3.5 below should thus be seen as rough summaries. However, before moving onto the specifics of the different domains, some general overall tendencies deserve attention.

3.1 Overall tendencies

Firstly, Seychelles is a culturally mixed society. According to the 2022 Seychelles Population and Housing Census (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022), almost 20% (19,920) of the total population (102,612) are non-Seychellois; Indians (8.9%) constituting by far the

largest group of non-Seychellois, followed by migrants from Sri Lanka (1.8%), Bangladesh (1.1%), Madagascar (1.1%), and Kenya (1.1%), as well as various other nationalities. The number of non-Seychellois in the population has more than doubled since the previous census in 2010, when this group constituted a mere 8.6% of the population. The rise in the number of non-Seychellois is a result of an increased reliance on foreign labour in recent years in key sectors such as construction, tourism, fisheries and education. Most of these workers are in Seychelles on short-term contracts, usually two years. In combination with over 300,000 visiting tourists each year, the overall result linguistically is that there is a heavy reliance on English as a lingua franca to communicate with visitors as well as colleagues. The current guest-worker situation also means that there are various pockets of language communities springing up that communicate in languages that are not the official languages of the Seychelles. These will, however, not be the focus of this article.

Another general observation regarding the language situation in Seychelles is the great pride that many attach to Kreol Seselwa and how the language is a primary factor in defining the Seychellois national identity. At the same time, however, there is a general tendency to downplay the instrumental value of the language in domains such as education and professional life, where English has much higher status. These tendencies have been noted in several studies (see Deutschmann, 2024; Fleischmann, 2008; Fleischmann-Schwarz and Nick, 2018; Zelime and Deutschmann, 2018).

Finally worth noting is the written vs. spoken dichotomy in Seychelles. While Kreol Seselwa is by far the most dominant language spoken in Seychellois homes (85.1% according to the Seychelles Population and Housing Census (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022)), its use in writing is much more limited. In this mode, English dominates. This is the case in most of the domains mentioned, as will be discussed below. Even in informal written contexts, such as social media, there is a strong tendency for English to be used, even though there is a lot of translanguaging going on whereby English and Kreol Seselwa are used intermittently, sometimes quite at random.

3.2 The language of politics

Prior to independence in 1976, French, and then English especially, were the languages of political debate and legislation. In preparation for independence, in 1975, the Seychelles House of Assembly declared English as its official working language but also allowed representatives to speak French or Kreol Seselwa. After independence in 1976, a policy of equal bilingualism in English and French was introduced. Later that year, Kreol Seselwa was formally admitted as a parliamentary language following an emotional debate (MacGregor, 2004). After the 1977 coup, the People's Assembly institutionalized a trilingual policy whereby Kreol Seselwa became the primary language of debate and legislation in the People's Assembly (Hoareau, 2010). However, the Assembly functioned verbally in Kreol Seselwa, while English remained the administrative language (MacGregor, 2004). With the return to multi-party democracy in 1993, the National Assembly reaffirmed Kreol Seselwa as its first official working language, intending to

reflect a shift from colonial linguistic dominance to full recognition of the national language in politics.

The formal status of Kreol Seselwa is stated in Article 11 of the National Assembly Standing Orders (2009) which regulates the Assembly's operational functions: 'The proceedings and debates of the Assembly will be in Creole, but a Minister or a Member may address the Assembly in English or French'. In accordance with the Standing Orders, all current official debates of the National Assembly are conducted, recorded, transcribed and published in Kreol Seselwa in official reports known as 'verbatim' on the National Assembly website². This is arguably the largest single corpus of contemporary written Kreol Seselwa to date. Many of the debates are also broadcasted in full on national radio and television. The National Assembly also has its own YouTube channel where all debates are published in full daily.³

Given the total dominance of Kreol Seselwa in the debates of the National Assembly, it is somewhat surprising to see that much of the communication related to administration takes place in English. Based on interviews with MPs, Anacoura (forthcoming) found that most e-mail correspondence dealing with practical matters is in English. Similarly, the National Assembly website⁴ is almost entirely written in English: for example, news flashes on visits of dignitaries etc. are all provided in English, as are publications dictating procedures, such as rules of procedures, standing orders, public hearing guides etc. Even the template frameworks for daily orders for National Assembly sittings are in English, this, in spite of the fact that specific content is given in Kreol Seselwa (see Figure 2 below). More specifically, in the extracts from the orders of the proceedings for 26 March, 2025, it is clear that headings, dates, titles etc. are all written in English, but then the specific questions to be asked are given in Kreol Seselwa (see the question in Extract 2 in Figure 1 below which translates to 'Can the Minister tell the Assembly how far the project Development for Port Victoria has reached?').

² <https://www.nationalassembly.sc/verbatim>

³ <https://www.youtube.com/c/TheNationalAssemblyofSeychelles>

⁴ <https://www.nationalassembly.sc/>

Figure 1: Extracts from the orders of procedures of the National Assembly, 26 March, 2025

Overall, Article 11, which establishes Kreol Seselwa as the primary language of the National Assembly, is followed in Assembly proceedings. Its influence, however, is limited to spoken interactions and does not extend to written and administrative functions, where English remains dominant. In the Seychelles' National Assembly, as in many other domains, there is thus a clear separation between the roles of the national languages along the spoken vs. written dimensions. Also to be noted is that, except for addresses to foreign francophone visiting dignitaries, and special occasions such as the International Francophonie Day, French is largely absent from the language of politics in Seychelles.

3.3 The language of the judiciary

Historically, the laws of Seychelles have evolved from the French and later the British legal systems. In 1993, the Constitution of the Republic of Seychelles⁵, formally granted the judiciary the power to draft, promulgate and uphold the law as endorsed by the National Assembly, as the legislative body, and the President and cabinet of ministers, as executive power. All laws to date are written in English and translations of these into Kreol Seselwa were not achieved until 2018. It is noteworthy that currently French does not officially feature at all as language of the contemporary laws of Seychelles. In terms of setting the context for the judiciary, it should also be noted here that over many years the judges, magistrates and lawyers were expatriates, often British, and so not Kreol speakers, as this has had considerable impact on the way language has developed in the judiciary.

Clause 1 of Article 4 of the Constitution stipulates that the 'National languages of Seychelles shall be Creole, English and French', which suggests that all three languages should figure in the Constitution and the legislation – acts central to a nation's being. However, Clause 1 is modified in Clause 2 of Article 4, stating that 'a person may use any of the national languages for any purpose but a law may provide for the use of any one or

⁵ <https://www.gov.sc/documents/constitution%20of%20seychelles%20.pdf>

more of the national languages for any specific purpose'. What this essentially means is that legislation can ensure that one or more specific language/s are only to be used in any specific public domain.

This is the case in the judiciary, where documents such as the Courts Act (CA), the Code of Civil Procedure (CCP) and the Criminal Procedure Code (CPC) explicitly name English as the language of court proceedings: see for example the following extracts from the CA, clause 1a and clause 3b of Article 65, and clause 1 of Article 256 of the CPC below.

CA, Article 65, clause 1a

Evidence or answers shall be taken down in writing in **English** by the Magistrate, or in his presence and hearing and under his personal direction and superintendence, and shall be signed by the Magistrate and shall form part of the record.

CA, Article 65, clause 3b

If he is represented by an advocate and the evidence or answers are given in a language other than **English**, and not understood by the advocate, it shall be interpreted to such advocate in **English**.

CPC, Article 256, clause 1

[...] if it appears to the court that any jurymen lacks proficiency in the **English language**, the court may, if it thinks fit, discharge such jurymen and proceed with the trial, provided that the number of the jury shall not fall below seven.

Although it is stated in the CA, CCP and CPC that interpreters should be available when needed, some formulations suggest that this is rather ad hoc.

CA, Article 65, clause c

Whenever such evidence or answers are given in **French or Creole**, the Magistrate may, if he is satisfied that he is sufficiently conversant with these languages, take down or cause to be taken down such evidence or answers in **English** in accordance with the provisions of the preceding sub-paragraphs without the use of a sworn interpreter.

According to evidence from a questionnaire sent out by the Creole Institute in 2010 (Anacoura, forthcoming) there is evidence that language issues such as mistranslations of evidence given in Kreol Seselwa frequently jeopardise legal justice (see also Twomey, 2017).

It is thus clear that the trilingual policy of the Constitution is not applied in the judiciary, where English totally dominates in written and spoken modes. Also noteworthy here is the fact that many lawyers operating in Seychelles are foreign nationals who do not speak Kreol Seselwa.

3.4 The languages' role in education

Throughout the colonial period, Kreol Seselwa was entirely prohibited in schools. Students faced punishments for using the language, including writing lines, formalized rituals intended to humiliate them, and even corporal punishment (Fleischmann, 2008, p.141). Following independence in 1976 and the left-wing coup d'état in 1977, the recognition of Kreol Seselwa as an official national language became central to the nation-building process. This move symbolized a deliberate break from the colonial past and the creation of a distinct cultural and linguistic identity (Ivanov et al., 2015). A key policy strategy in this effort was integrating Kreol Seselwa into the education system.

Consequently, in the late 1970s and early 1980s, significant efforts in status and corpus planning were undertaken to elevate the status of Kreol Seselwa. This process involved the formalization of its orthography, grammar, and lexicon, alongside the translation of key literary works into Kreol Seselwa (see Fleischmann, 2008, pp.58-67 for further details). Kreol Seselwa was officially introduced in education as both a language of instruction and an academic subject. This implementation required the development of learning materials and the training of teachers. Despite these challenges, Seychelles became the first Creole-speaking nation to adopt a Creole language as a medium of instruction in January 1982 (Siegel, 2005). Initially, Kreol Seselwa was used as the language of instruction from Primary Grades 1 to 4 and was taught as a separate subject up to Primary Grade 6. Furthermore, it became the sole language of instruction for Social Education, Physical Education, the Creative Arts, and Religion throughout the compulsory years of schooling. Kreol Seselwa thus formed part of a trilingual policy where English remained the language of instruction in academic subjects after Primary Grade 4, but where Kreol Seselwa was a subject in its own right until Primary Grade 6 and had a primary role in more practical subjects. French, the third official language, was taught as a foreign language from Primary Grade 1 (Campling, Confiance and Purvis, 2011; Purvis, 2004).

Teaching young children in their mother tongue had significant positive effects (Fox, 2010; Campling, Confiance and Purvis, 2011; Bickerton, 1990). Comparisons between the final cohorts taught in English and the first groups instructed under the new system revealed that the latter outperformed the former in nearly all subjects, including French and the sciences. Notably, students taught in Kreol Seselwa achieved similar results in English as those previously educated exclusively in English (Bickerton, 1990, p.48). Additionally, literacy rates saw a dramatic increase following the implementation of mother-tongue instruction (Campling, Confiance and Purvis, 2011, p.51).

Despite its status as a formal language, the acceptance of Kreol Seselwa was not universal, even among its native speakers. Following concerns raised in the 1994 Language Policy Review Committee report, which was based on interviews with teachers, parents, and the public, the use of Kreol Seselwa as language of instruction was reduced to Primary Grades 1–2 in 1996. Arguably, this reform had a negative impact on overall school performance, which according to Fox (2010, p.17) ‘nosedives in Primary 3 and 4’ when English is introduced as medium of instruction.

Several factors influenced this decision. Policymakers argued that increased exposure to English through media, such as television, better prepared children for an earlier transition to English as the language of instruction. Additionally, teachers reported difficulties in transitioning from Kreol Seselwa to English, stating that they had to ‘re-teach’ basic concepts after Primary Grade 4, as students struggled to understand them in English. A lack of resources further hindered the expansion of Kreol Seselwa in education. Producing textbooks across all subjects and grade levels was seen as impractical for a country with fewer than 100,000 inhabitants, and there was also a shortage of teachers trained in Kreol Seselwa (Ivanov et al., 2015).

Ideological factors likely contributed to the diminished role of Kreol Seselwa in education as well. Political shifts in the early 1990s, particularly the establishment of the ‘Third Republic’ in 1993 and the transition to multi-party democracy, played a role. According to Laversuch (2008, p.377), during this period, Seychelles moved from a state-controlled economy reliant on Soviet aid to a more open, liberal economy, prioritizing global economic integration. Language policies favouring English and French were largely driven by economic motives, aiming to strengthen international business and diplomatic ties (Laversuch, 2008, p.378).

Whatever the reasons, from 1996 to date, the role of Kreol Seselwa in education has become increasingly limited. Although it is clearly stated in the National Curriculum Framework (Ministry of Education, 2013) that Kreol Seselwa can be used in this capacity throughout the education system, there are indications that this is becoming less and less acceptable. Several studies confirm this.

For example, Zelime and Deutschmann (2016) show that while the status of the three languages is equal in the National Curriculum Framework, clear differences in the power and functions of the languages emerge in the subject curricula. From the descriptions, it is evident that the role of Kreol Seselwa is peripheral and mainly serves as a transition language, which is used to develop basic learning skills and thereby help young children to enter the more complex cognitive universe of the ex-colonial languages. Other evidence of the diminishing role of Kreol Seselwa in Education includes a cabinet decision taken in 2017 to start teaching the subject of Mathematics in English from Primary Grade 1 (Deutschmann and Zelime, 2021).

In another study on language beliefs, attitudes and classroom practices of primary school teachers, Zelime and Deutschmann (2018) show that while the vast majority (98%) of teachers used Kreol Seselwa for everyday oral communication, they were overall quite negative towards its role in education. A striking 96.5% of the respondents would have liked to see English introduced as language of instruction even earlier in the system (even at preschool level) (p.139). A clear majority of the teachers thought the advantages of teaching in English outweighed the disadvantages in the current system. Kreol Seselwa was generally viewed as a less prestigious language than English, particularly in professional contexts.

Current language-in-education policies and teachers' attitudes also affect learners' attitudes towards Kreol Seselwa. In their study of learners' attitudes towards the three national languages, the findings of Deutschmann and Zelime (2015), clearly showed that students of all ages were very positive towards Kreol Seselwa. These positive attitudes were particularly noticeable in the primary grades where Kreol Seselwa was favoured over English and French in all four literacy skill domains. These attitudes were also mirrored in the Primary 6 national assessments, where Kreol Seselwa was the subject students performed best in. There was, however, a clear change in attitude towards writing and reading (but not listening or speaking) in Kreol Seselwa once students entered the secondary level. Secondary students were significantly more negative towards reading and writing in Kreol Seselwa. The more negative attitudes towards Kreol Seselwa as a written language seem to reflect Kreol Seselwa ceasing to be an academic subject after Primary Grade 6.

In general, English is the dominant language in education, especially in written form. The role of Kreol Seselwa in education has gradually declined since its introduction in the 1980s. It is now only the medium of instruction in the first two years of primary school and ceases to be a school subject after Primary 6. Mathematics is taught in English from Primary 1. French has the status of a foreign language in the school system.

3.5 The language of media

There are several media production companies in Seychelles. The most established local radio and television producer is a national public broadcaster, the *Seychelles Broadcasting Corporation* (SBC), which produces non-commercial radio and television for a local audience. There are also several commercial radio stations and one commercial television company, *Téléseel*. The largest newspaper is the *Seychelles Nation*, which is publicly funded and claims to be politically unaffiliated. Other papers include *Today in Seychelles*, *The Seychelles Independent Newspaper*, *Le Seychellois Hebdo* and *The People*, and these are either privately owned or politically affiliated.

In her analysis of 251 programme guides of the SBC television and radio programmes, Anacoura (forthcoming) shows how a large proportion of radio programmes (40%) are monolingual productions in Kreol Seselwa. Furthermore, 41% of radio programmes contain trilingual content, with Kreol Seselwa and English being the most prominent languages. Monolingual English programmes make up 13% of the radio content, while monolingual French programmes only make up 9% of the radio broadcasts. The same study shows that in television, multilingual material is largely absent. In this medium, English programmes constitute the largest proportion of what is broadcasted (62% of the program content), but many of these programmes are foreign productions. Programmes in Kreol Seselwa, makes up 30% of the content, while monolingual French features in 7% of the content.

In contrast, newspapers are totally dominated by English (Anacoura, forthcoming). In her analysis of 218 articles and adverts in the largest national newspaper, the *Seychelles Nation*, 85% of all material is monolingual English content. Articles written in French constitutes a mere 5.5% of the material and Kreol Seselwa only 3%. The remaining content is multilingual (primarily adverts).

Again, the above shows a clear divide between language practices in the spoken and written modes. On television, and especially radio, Kreol Seselwa has a very strong presence. In newspapers, however, it hardly figures at all. In media as in many other domains, French has a marginal presence.

An area where Kreol Seselwa is gaining ground as a written medium, however, is social media. Here, there is a lot of codeswitching/translanguaging present, between and within the same comments. Below is an example of a typical thread in a local discussion forum.

Figure 2: Translanguaging in discussion forum on Facebook

The example above in Figure 2 is quite typical for communication in social media. In the discussion, an upcoming press conference on a sensitive matter is being discussed. The initial threads (Persons 1 and 2) are in English. Person 3 starts in English (Yes) and then switches to Kreol Seselwa ('Don't be scared, say it all'), whereupon Person 4 responds in Kreol Seselwa ('They have gone and touched [incorrectly spelt] a wasps' nest. Be careful they don't get stung'). This type of translanguaging is quite typical in discussions that concern local events. Another interesting phenomenon visible in social media is the growing use of what Pejakovic et al. (2025) refer to as 'chatspeak writing'. Chatspeak involves almost systematic shortening of words by removing vowels, eg. *Mon pa konen* ('I don't know') > *Mn p kn*.

In summary, Kreol Seselwa and English hold equal roles in spoken media (local radio and television productions). Written media, however, are completely dominated by English. In

social media, written Kreol Seselwa is frequently used alongside English. French has a marginal role in all of these media contexts.

3.6 Language usage in the domain of religion

Approximately 75% of the Seychelles population are Christians, of which 82% are Roman Catholics (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). Until independence, religion in the Catholic church was practiced entirely in French, reflecting the historical French influence, and this practice partly remains as religious services often incorporate French in hymns and liturgical readings. In more recent years, however, the translation of the Bible and other religious texts into Kreol Seselwa has reinforced its role in religious life, and Kreol Seselwa dominates the less formal parts of sermons in the Catholic church. Some Anglican and other Christian denominations use English, especially in sermons, youth ministries, and formal church documents. Meanwhile, newer religious groups, including Evangelical and Pentecostal churches, frequently use English, particularly in sermons and worship songs, due to international religious influences. Various Indian languages dominate in the second biggest religion of Seychelles, Hinduism, which is practiced by 5.5% of the population.

In summary, religion is the one domain where French still holds a strong position. Kreol Seselwa has, however, gained substantial ground in this domain, to gradually become the dominant language of religious practices after independence.

3.7 Language usage in informal domains – ‘the street’ and family life

The language that predominates in informal communication in Seychelles is Kreol Seselwa. According to the 2022 Census (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022), 85.1% of the population list it as the first language spoken in their homes followed by English at 8%. A mere 0,5% of the population list French as their first language. This dominance of Kreol Seselwa has been confirmed in many studies (Deutschmann, 2024a; 2024b; Zelime and Deutschmann, 2018; Hoareau, 2010; Fleischmann; 2008). In effect, one can almost talk of Seychelles as a relatively homogenous monolingual society in the spoken mode.

When it comes to public signage, however, English dominates. In her analysis of 668 public signs that included commercial signs, public information notices, shop signs etc., Anacoura (forthcoming) found that English dominated the linguistic landscape, where 64% of all signs were written in English only, and 27% contained English and other national languages (i.e. signs written in more than one language). Monolingual French signs constituted a mere 4% while monolingual signs written in Kreol Seselwa made up only 3% of the sample. This again confirms Kreol Seselwa’s weak position as written medium and the marginal role of French in the Seychelles language ecology.

4. Summary and discussion of language ideologies

Overall, Kreol Seselwa can be described as the primary mode of oral communication in informal contexts, whereas English holds a strong position in more formal oral contexts. This balance shifts across domains. In the judiciary, for example, English is the sole language used for official oral communication, whereas Kreol Seselwa is the language used for all debates in the National Assembly. In education, Kreol Seselwa is the medium of instruction in the first two years of schooling and then English takes over. In the written mode, English dominates almost totally, with the exception of the Kreol Seselwa transcriptions of all political debates in the Verbatim of the National Assembly. French has a marginal role in the Seychelles language ecology, limited to religion and some cultural contexts such as traditional songs.

Unravelling Seychellois language ideologies towards their mother tongue (Kreol Seselwa) and English is complex. Attitudes are often highly incongruous. On the one hand, several studies confirm the fact that Seychellois are proud of their language, that it defines their national identity and that it has a given role in the national language policy (Deutschmann, 2024a; 2024b; Fleischmann, 2008; Fleischmann-Schwarz and Nick, 2018; Hoareau, 2010). On the other hand, there are very negative attitudes that remain related to the formal role of Kreol Seselwa in education and professional life (Deutschmann, 2024a; 2024b; Zelime and Deutschmann, 2018). This schizophrenic ideology may arguably be a result of the historical heritage. Under colonial rule, Kreol Seselwa was not recognized as a language at all, and this attitude somehow remains as a colonial hangover. At the same time, elevating Kreol Seselwa to a formal language and part of the trilingual national policy, was a way of marking a break with the colonial past and the establishment of a new cultural and linguistic autonomous identity after the 1977 coup. Kreol Seselwa thus became politicized. Given the unpopularity of the left-wing regime among substantial parts of the population, it may be that this spilled over to affect attitudes towards language reforms undertaken by the regime.

There is also a pragmatic aspect to consider when evaluating language ideologies. There is no doubt that English carries with it enormous benefits when it comes to access to international education and professional opportunities. It is this fact that seems to motivate parents to send their children to international schools and communicate with their children in English (see Deutschmann 2024a; 2024b).

Attitudes towards French in Seychelles are not as favourable as towards English and Kreol Seselwa. Rudström (2017), for example, notes that none of the respondents in his study on language and identity expressed positive attitudes towards French. Some did not even acknowledge that they spoke or understood French (p.22). Many have speculated as to why French is so unpopular given the historical connections. A popular explanation is that French is associated with slavery, oppression and the *Grand Blancs* ruling classes (McAter, 2008; Fleischmann, 2008).

5. Conclusion

Looking ahead one can speculate on how the language ecology of Seychelles will evolve in the coming years. There are many indications that Seychelles will become more multilingual with the influx of migrant workers. This may further strengthen the role of English in informal contexts. There are also marginal indications that English is becoming more common as a first language among the native population. Kreol Seselwa has declined from 90.4% as a primary language to 85% in the last twelve years (National Bureau of Statistics, 2022). One reason may be that some parents opt to speak English with their children to prepare them for school (Deutschmann, 2024b). English is also becoming more dominant in education. I do not, however, foresee that Kreol Seselwa is under threat, at least not as an oral language. Its role as a written medium and the elevation of its status in education and academia is however entirely dependent on language planning efforts. Whether future governments decide to invest in its status or not, is difficult to predict. Also note that institutions such as such as Lakademi Kreol Sesel and the Creole Language and Culture Research Institute at the University of Seychelles also play important roles in deciding future policy directions. As for French, I cannot see that its status will change in the future. In education, the language holds the status of a foreign language and its role in other domains is minimal. It could even be removed from the trilingual policy given its marginal role, but this is highly unlikely given its historical status.

There are great gaps and opportunities for further research into the sociolinguistics of Seychelles. An area of particular interest is the role of written Kreol Seselwa in social media. Here it would also be interesting to study how usage in this domain affects orthographic norms. Another area that merits study is current changes in Kreol Seselwa. There is much talk about the increasing inclusion of English vocabulary and expressions in Kreol Seselwa and many see this as a threat to the language (a view I do not share – a strength of Creole languages is that they are open to borrowing vocabulary). A final area of relevant research would be a current survey of the use of spoken English vs. Kreol Seselwa in working and social life. One hypothesis would be that the increased influx of expatriate workers means that Seychellois are increasingly using English in everyday conversations at work. It would also be interesting to investigate language experiences and ideologies from the expatriate perspective.

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